

Level of Infestation of Plantain Banana Cultivars by the Black Weevil *Cosmopolites sordidus* (Germar) in the Kisangani Region, Democratic Republic of Congo

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the level of infestation of plantain bananas by the black weevil *Cosmopolites sordidus* across three cultivars in the Kisangani region. The cultivars studied were 'Libanga likale' (Musa AAB of the false horn type), 'Litete' (Musa AAB of the French type), and 'Lokusu' (Musa AAB of the true horn type). The study focused on the rate of attack, the average number of adult individuals per plant, and the severity of the attack. The results indicated that all cultivars were susceptible but significantly different from one another regarding the rate of infestation and the number of adult *Cosmopolites* per infested plant ($P < 0.05$). The extent of damage varied with the bulb diameter of the infested subjects. The cultivar 'Litete' was the most affected, with an infestation rate of 77.5%, hosting an average of 164 adult *Cosmopolites* per infested plant. Within the same cultivar, plants with a small bulb diameter (16-24 cm) were the most sensitive. These findings suggest that the vigour of the bulb influences the level of infestation of plantain bananas.

Keywords: *plantain banana, Musa AAB, weevils, level, infestation.*

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Introduction

The cultivation of plantain bananas is an essential agricultural activity in many tropical countries due to its dual role in subsistence and commerce. In the poorest countries of Africa, Latin America, and Asia, nearly 90% of the production is consumed locally (Lassoudière, 2012).

In West and Central Africa, plantain cultivation is fundamental to many subsistence systems, playing a critical role in nutrition and contributing to the economy of farmers. As a significant source of vitamins and minerals, it accounts for over half of the daily caloric intake, greatly contributing to food security and

nutrition for millions of people (Deloné, 2014). Proceeds from banana sales are often used to finance education and healthcare expenses, enabling the rural poor to participate in social and community activities. When combined with other crops, banana cultivation helps prevent soil erosion in fragile ecosystems while requiring less labour (Van Den Put, 1981; F.A.O., 2012).

Aside from poor soil fertility, a low genetic base, and other socio-economic factors, the productivity of this crop is limited by pests and diseases. In the Democratic Republic of Congo, the production of bananas and plantains dropped from 1,666,430 tonnes in 1996 to 485,560 tonnes in 2009 (Makala (nd), SNSA, 2010). This crop, of paramount importance for food and economic security for the population in the DRC, faces constant parasitic threats (Bakelana & Muyunga, 1998). Among the main constraints to its production, the black weevil, *Cosmopolites sordidus*, leads to significant yield losses (Stover & Buddenhagen, 1986; Stover & Simmonds, 1987; Simmonds, 1994; Gold & al., 2005).

In the larval stage, *Cosmopolites sordidus* feeds on the bulbs of banana plants, burrowing galleries within them; it destroys the centre and the parts near the roots. Due to damage to the roots and bulbs, the adult banana plant collapses, resulting in decreased production (Stover & Buddenhagen, 1986; Stover & Simmonds, 1987; Simmonds, 1994; Gold & al., 2005).

This rate can significantly increase if the infestation is old or if the plantation is poorly maintained, exceeding 50% losses (Lavabre, 1992). Notable losses are also reported where banana plantations are maintained on the same soil for many years or in cases of replanting (Deloné, 2014). However, literature frequently mentions varietal differences in sensitivity to this pest (Cuillé, 1950; Vilardebo, 1973; Pavis, 1993; Seshu Reddy & Lubega, 1993; Fogain & Prince, 1994).

The present study aims to evaluate the level of infestation among the main cultivars of plantain bananas in the region surrounding the city of Kisangani. Given the low level of technical support characterising peasant agriculture in the DRC, the infestation by the black bulb weevil in plantain cultivars is expected to be particularly high.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Investigations were conducted from April 2022 to January 2023 in the region surrounding the city of Kisangani along the following roads: Kisangani – Yangambi (from kilometre point 18 to 35 starting from the Lindi ferry); Kisangani – Buta (from kilometre point 9 to 36); Kisangani – Opala (from kilometre point 8 to 25); and Kisangani – Bafwasende (from kilometre point 21 to 40), as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Map Showing the Democratic Republic of Congo and the City of Kisangani in the Tshopo Province (Google Maps) with the Surveyed Area Outlined in Red

The city of Kisangani is located in the central Congolese basin at 0°31'N and 25°11'E, with an average altitude of 396 m. It enjoys an Af climate according to the Köppen classification, with annual precipitation ranging between 1600 and 1800 mm. The average temperature varies between 24 and 25°C, and the relative humidity is quite high at 85%. Monthly sunshine averages range from 30 to 55% (Crabbe & al., 1971). The overall eco-climatic data, along with Kisangani's proximity to the Equator, gives it an equatorial climate.

The selection of this investigation area is justified, on one hand, by the predominance of banana cultivation in these environments and, on the other hand, by ease of access. Three sites (villages) spaced approximately 5 to 8 km apart along each route, making a total of 12 sites, were chosen.

Methodology

Plant Material

This study focused on the most represented plantain cultivars in the region (Dhed'a, 2010): Libanga likale (AAB, false horn), Litete (AAB, dark French), and Lokusu (AAB, true horn) at the flowering or fruiting stage in case cultivation, as the female prefers plants that have reached the flowering or production stage for laying eggs (Treverrow & al., 1992; Abera et al., 1999; Gold & Messiaen, 2000).

Methodological Approach

The approach used in conducting the survey was as follows:

- Selection of adult plants for investigation;
- Identification of the vernacular names of the cultivars through questioning;
- Assessment of the infestation level of each cultivar through peeling.

The proposed technique for estimating *C. sordidus* attacks is based on the observation of galleries dug by larvae in the stumps (Vilardebo, 1973).

The method for detecting infestation involved peeling bulbs to expose the galleries of the weevils and the adult forms of *Cosmopolites sordidus*, facilitating counting. Observations were made on a sample of 30 stumps per cultivar and per surveyed village, amounting to 360 stumps per cultivar across the 12 sites. Infested banana plants are those that show perforations in the bulbs after peeling.

The attack rate is determined using the following formula:

$$T. A. (\%) = \frac{\text{Number of infested plants}}{\text{Total number of surveyed plants}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

To assess the influence of banana plant vigour on weevil infestation, three diameter classes at 30 cm from the collar were considered: 16-24 cm; 24.1 – 32 cm; 32.1-40 cm. The classes were established based on the two extreme diameters observed in the field. Only banana plants in the flowering phase or bearing bunches in case cultivation were selected. The collar diameter was determined from the circumference using a measuring tape, utilising the circumference-diameter ratio.

The level of infestation by the weevil in a plot is evaluated through peeling. This operation is performed on recently harvested plants (0-15 days post-harvest). The outer part of the banana stump is progressively peeled while counting the number of larvae and adults found. Additionally, a transverse cut above the

bulb is made to count the observed galleries (Viljoen & al., 2017). The determination of the infestation level was based on the rating scale of Vilardebo (1973), which is presented as follows:

Level 0: no galleries;

Level 5: presence of gallery traces;

Level 10: intermediate infestation between 5 and 20;

Level 20: presence of galleries on about a quarter of the stump perimeter;

Level 30: intermediate score between 20 and 40;

Level 40: presence of galleries on about half of the stump perimeter;

Level 60: presence of galleries on about three-quarters of the stump perimeter;

Level 100: presence of galleries around the entire stump perimeter.

The values of the rating scale are representative of a certain state of the stump. The stronger the attack, the more extensive the area showing galleries, and the higher the level of infestation.

For the number of adult *Cosmopolites* per plant, individuals were counted through simple enumeration after peeling.

A two-factor analysis of variance followed by Bonferroni post-tests was used to compare the different cultivars and diameter classes using Graph Pad Prism software (Graph Pad Software, San Diego, California, USA). The significance level for differences was set at 5%

Results and Discussion

Infestation Rate

All the cultivars studied are sensitive and infested to varying degrees. The severity of the damage varies within the same genotype, not only among the cultivars but also according to the diameter at the base of the bulb, as indicated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Infestation Rate According to Cultivars and Bulb Diameter Ranges
Legend: A = diameter of 16-24 cm; B = diameter of 24.1-32 cm; C = diameter of 32.1-40 cm.

Overall, the cultivar Litete (AAB French sombre) is the most attacked, with 78.1%, followed by Libanga likale (AAB faux corne) at 73.8%, and finally Lokusu (AAB vrai corne) at 64.6%. For all cultivars, the banana plants with a small diameter (16 to 24 cm) are the most attacked. The analysis of variance shows a significant difference between the cultivars ($F = 4.110$; $df = 2$; $P = 0.0193$). This confirms the findings of Pavis & Lemaire (1998), who emphasise that there is a significant difference in sensitivity within the same genomic group. The duration of the vegetative cycle of the cultivars is an important factor in this infestation. Thus, the cultivar Litete, which has a longer cycle (14 to 16 months), is more exposed to attacks than the other two, which have a cycle of 10 to 12 months.

Overall, a significant interaction exists between the cultivars and the different bulb diameters ($F = 2.791$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.0304$).

At the diameter level, a significant difference is noted between the cultivars Libanga likale and Litete for the diameter range of 16-24 cm; and between Libanga likale and Lokusu for the diameter range of 32.1-40 cm ($P < 0.05$). For the other diameter ranges, the difference is not significant among the cultivars. These results corroborate those of Balachowsky (1963), who highlights that varieties with larger development and larger stumps are more resistant to attacks from black weevils than smaller ones.

Treverrow et al. (1992) report that stressed and less vigorous subjects are the most attacked. Based on the vigour of the banana plants, Pavis and Lemaire (1998) as well as Rukazambuga (1996) mention that certain sensitive varieties may be quite attacked, but their vigour allows them to withstand the presence of numerous galleries on the stump. Overall, these results show that vigorous banana plants are more resistant to attacks from this pest than weaker individuals. It further suggests that if soil fertility conditions are ensured to promote good vigour in the banana plants, damage can be significantly reduced.

Average Number of Adult Cosmopolites per Plant

The average number of adult Cosmopolites per infested plant ranged from 63 to 164, with the highest count observed in the cultivar Litete (164), followed by Libanga Likale (139), and finally Lokusu, which had 63 adult Cosmopolites, as reported in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. Number of Adult Cosmopolites by Cultivar

Variance analysis shows a highly significant difference between the cultivars ($F= 12$; $df= 2$; $P=0.0001$). The comparison of means using the Bonferroni test indicates a highly significant difference between the cultivars Litete and Lokusu, a very significant difference between Libanga Likale and Lokusu, and finally, a non-significant difference between Litete and Libanga Likale.

The population levels of this pest have been the subject of several studies employing different methods: using capture-mark-recapture techniques, Delattre (1980) estimated these densities in two different plots at 2600 individuals/ha and 15,600 individuals/ha, which translates to densities of 10 to 337 adults per plant; in Uganda, the densities of *Cosmopolites* were estimated to be between 6 and 17 individuals per plant (Gold et al., 2001) through mass trapping.

However, it is challenging to distinguish the effect of trapping efficiency from that of population growth.

A thorough analysis of these results implicates several explanatory factors: the lifestyle of this insect is characterised by positive thigmotaxis (Delattre, 1980; Treverrow & Bedding, 1993). Being reliant on its host for an extended period, under favourable conditions, population centres develop and multiply. As populations increase, they can become considerable, severely affecting the banana plants.

Multiple generations may then succeed one another on the same plant. A second explanatory factor is that the banana plant is attractive to other adult *Cosmopolites* in the meantime. Lastly, this insect produces an aggregation pheromone (sordidine) that attracts other male and female individuals (Cerda et al., 1995; Lemaire, 1996; Fernando et al., 1999; Tinzaara et al., 2005) in the vicinity. Consequently, the number of individuals observed on a plant results from both population growth and the aggregation phenomenon.

Level of Infestation

Overall, the level of infestation ranges between levels 10 and 20 on the rating scale, concentrated around a quarter of the bulb's circumference, except for the sites Bambane, Bawi, and Bandjuade, all located along the Kisangani-Buta axis, where it reaches level 40 (presence of galleries on approximately half of the plant's circumference), as indicated in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Level of Infestation of Banana Cultivars by *C. sordidus* According to Survey Sites

The high level of infestation along the Kisangani-Buta axis (sites Bambane, Bawi, and Bandjuade) can be explained by the age and intensity of banana cultivation along this route, which provides a significant share of the consumption for the city of Kisangani.

Conclusion

The present study aimed to evaluate the level of infestation of the main cultivars of plantain banana in the vicinity of the city of Kisangani by *Cosmopolites sordidus*. The results obtained indicate that all the cultivars studied are susceptible to the black weevil, with significant damage varying according to the size of the bulb at the base. The cultivar "Litete" is the most sensitive, with an infestation rate of 78.1%, followed by "Libanga likale" at 73.8% and "Lokusu" at 64.6%. The same cultivar "Litete" hosts the highest number of adult *Cosmopolites* (164) compared to the others. For all cultivars, banana plants with small bulbs (17 to 24 cm) are the most attacked compared to the more vigorous ones (bulb diameter > 30 cm). These results suggest the potential for cultural methods that promote the vigour of banana plants to reduce the impact of this pest. However, they need to be confirmed by artificial infestation trials.

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